

Beyond Marriage in India: Laws, Social Realities, And Youth Attitudes Toward Live-In Relationships

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Abstract:

In this contemporary India we can see a trend of live-in relationships which is becoming very common and popular in Indian urban life, mainly among young people in cities. Live-in relationship means where two adults live together without getting legally married. Indian society has traditionally great importance to marriage, but due to changing lifestyles, education, jobs and social media all these have influenced new relationship choices amongst today's generation. This paper studies and analyses the legal position of live-in relationships in India, the problems faced by couples and the changing attitude of Generation Z. The study is based on books, court judgments, and research articles. It finds that although courts have given some protection to live-in partners, there is no clear law in India that fully protects their rights and social acceptance is still limited in many parts of the country.

Keywords: *Live-in relationships, generation z, India, women's protection.*

Introduction:

Marriage in India holds a sacred and it is considered as an important institution as it is connected with religion, culture, and family traditions, it's not about just two individuals but two families. However, in recent years, in urban areas couples have started choosing live-in relationships instead of getting formally married. A live-in relationship means where two adults live together in a long-term relationship without any formal marriage, this type of relationships is not illegal in India but as they are not fully guided by a specific law this creates confusion about rights related to property, maintenance, and children. At the same time, young people, mainly Generation Z, are showing more acceptance toward this form of relationship. This paper studies the legal position, social challenges, and youth perspective on live-in relationships in India.

Objectives:

To understand the legal status of live-in relationships in India and the challenges faced by couples. It also aims to examine court decisions, study social attitudes, and understand how Gen Z views such relationships.

Review of Literature:

Many researchers as well as experts have studied how live-in relationships are changing in India. Their work focuses on three main area like the law, women's safety, and the views of young people.

Banerjee (2018) who explains how Indian courts have slowly started recognizing live-in relationships in certain cases.

Sharma (2020) who discusses how women in such relationships often face more problems than men, especially financial and social insecurity.

Reports from The United Nations Women (UN Women, 2021) also highlights the need to protect women from violence and exploitation, even if they are not legally married.

Researchers also note that globalisation and social media have influenced young people's attitudes, making live-in relationships more visible in cities. However, there is still a lack of clear legal protection.

Research Methodology:

This research is based on secondary data. It includes study of Supreme Court judgments, Indian laws, books, research articles and reports. The study uses legal analysis to understand how courts interpret live-in relationships. No field survey or interviews were conducted for this study.

Scope of the Study:

The focus is only on India, where the paper studies legal recognition, social challenges, and the views of young people, especially Gen Z towards live-in relationships.

Legal Status of Live-in Relationships in India:

In India there is no separate or different law for live-in relationships but courts have given some recognition to this institution. For example, In *S. Khushboo v. Kanniammal* (2010), the Supreme Court said that if both individuals in live-in relationships are consenting adults it is not illegal. The Court stated, under Article 21 of the constitution adults have right to choose how they want to live.

In another example, *Indra Sarma v. V.K.V. Sarma*, the Court explained that a live-in relationship can be considered similar to marriage. The Court said that the factors like living together for a long time, sharing a household, and presenting themselves as a couple are important.

In such situations protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 also protects women in relationships that are “in the nature of marriage” which means that a woman in a live-in relationship can ask for help or protection from abuse and may also claim maintenance in some cases. Courts have also given legal rights to children born from such relationships. But because of there is no clear law, many issues depend on court decisions.

Legal and Practical Challenges:

Even though courts have given some protection, many problems remain. There are no automatic property rights between partners. If a couple separates, there is no proper legal procedure like divorce. Women may find it difficult to prove that they were in a long-term relationship. Maintenance and inheritance rights are not always guaranteed. Because of this, partners, especially women, may feel insecure.

Social Challenges in India:

Live-in relationships still face social criticism in many Indian societies. Many families do not accept such relationships due to social pressure hence couples may face housing problems, as some landlords refuse to rent to unmarried couples. Women often face more judgment from society than men. In rural and conservative areas, such relationships are strongly opposed. While in big cities like Mumbai, Pune, Bengaluru and Delhi, we can see acceptance for such relationships which is slowly increasing. Education and economic independence have helped in changing attitudes in urban areas.

Gen Z Perspective in India:

Modern Indian youth, Gen Z, are prioritizing personal compatibility and career readiness over early marriage. They often utilize live-in relationships as a tool for evaluating a partner's temperament and lifestyle fit before getting into a life-long commitment. We can see this cultural shift largely in urban areas as there is

more exposure and social media influence, than it did for previous generations. Whereas we cannot see this acceptance in rural areas as traditional values still dominate India's smaller towns. A major concern which is highlighted in this study is that while Gen Z is comfortable living together, they often lack a formal understanding of their legal standing, which can lead to complications during relationship disputes.

Findings:

The study finds that live-in relationships are not illegal in India but they are not clearly defined by law. Courts have provided some protection, especially to women and children. Whereas, legal rights related to property and maintenance are not fully secure. There is social acceptance in cities but remains limited in rural areas, also Gen Z shows more acceptance of live-in relationships, but legal knowledge among youth is still low.

Significance of the Study:

This study is important because it connects legal issues with social change in India. It shows how today generation thinking is changing while the law is still developing and it also highlights the need to protect women and children in such relationships.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the way young Indians like Generation Z look at commitment or marriage is changing rapidly. While traditional marriage remains as a core part of Indian culture, but staying together without a wedding has become a

practical choice for many in big cities. Although the Supreme Court of India has made it clear that living together is not a illegal, the lack of a specific "Live-in Law" still it creates many hurdles for individuals. The study shows that there are some protections that exist under the Domestic Violence Act (2005), but partners still face problems when it comes to property, money matters and the future of their children, also we can see a huge difference between urban youth and rural youth in India, where in cities, education and jobs have made people more open-minded, but in smaller towns, social pressure and traditional family values are still very strong.

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